

COMPASS

Report on dataset on best-available methods and climate-datasets (for climate attribution)

Deliverable 2.1

29th November 2024

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Executive summary

There are currently many well-established climate attribution methodologies for single driver extremes, however, there is very little literature on more complex extremes such as compound, sequences and cascading hazard events. The main goal of COMPASS is to develop a harmonized methodological framework for climate and impact attribution of such complex extremes. This report D2.1, presents a critical overview of well-established attribution methodologies and datasets used, including their potential to be adapted to more complex extremes. This lays the foundation and contributes to the work package 2 Objective to *'Develop, test and compare attribution methods for compound extreme weather-related events'*. This report also complements deliverable D1.1 from Work Package 1, that reports on workflows for the characterization of compound extremes and an inventory of currently available datasets.

In the report we discuss the value of different attribution approaches and the complementary information each one provides. The established methodologies for each approach are examined in detail, including both the suitability and challenges involved in adapting them for more complex extremes. The final part lists the attribution methods that are being considered for each of our complex extremes Use Cases.

Complex extremes require analysis of multiple variables and hence are reliant on a methodology that can be adapted to take more than one variable into account and are able to integrate sufficiently large datasets to robustly capture enough of the multi-variate extremes. We identify several methods that have potential to meet both requirements and give guidance on the methodologies that we think are likely to be easiest to adapt for complex extremes. However, given the wide range of complex extremes being covered, it is likely that the best available method will have to be determined on a case-by-case basis.

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1. Introduction

Climate attribution studies investigate how human influence has changed the magnitude and/or the frequency of either a class of events or a specific event (Stott et al., 2016). Since the first climate attribution study for a specific event (Stott et al., 2004), a wide range of attribution methods have been created and developed. Most attribution methods have focused on univariate problems so far and hence in many cases need to be adapted or developed further to deal with the difficulties of compound event attribution. Some of the extra challenges involved in compound attribution include having enough samples for compound events, capturing the joint dependencies between variables and applying multivariate bias correction (Zscheischler et al., 2019; Bevacqua, et al 2023). These challenges will need to be addressed to make robust attribution statements. Different attribution methods can also ask very different questions of the event in question, what is referred to as ‘Framing’ and can therefore lead to different answers. It is therefore important to understand what the intended attribution question is when choosing the method. Attribution methods span a wide range of conditioning from probabilistic (unconditional) to storyline approaches (extremely conditioned). These tend to focus on either changes in both the large-scale dynamics and thermodynamic aspect, or just the thermodynamic aspect respectively.

The goal of Work Package 2 is to develop a physical understanding of the drivers of compound extremes using weather type analysis and subsequently apply a variety of event attribution methods to consider relevant impacts of compound events. This deliverable, “D2.1 – Report on dataset on best-available methods and climate datasets”, aims to provide initial guidance on which current attribution methods are best suited to compound attribution for both conditional and unconditional approaches, given the availability of data. This deliverable is closely linked to and follows Deliverable D1.1 ‘Guidelines for compound extremes modelling in current and future climates’, using its input on available datasets. By doing so, it contributes to two of COMPASS specific objectives (SO) to “Develop, test and compare attribution methods for compound extreme weather-related events” and “Work towards development of a framework to identify, assess and understand large scale drivers and mechanisms which give rise to compound extremes”. COMPASS focusses on compound events associated with several hazards including rainfall, storm surge, tropical cyclones, windstorms, wildfires, heatwaves, drought and saltwater intrusion. Additionally, COMPASS will consider a variety of attribution methods including conditional and unconditional. In this deliverable, we also underline how the attribution methods discussed could be applied to the individual Use Cases.

1.1 Terminology

The terms “**compound events**” and “**compound extremes**” describe events or extremes that contain at least one of the following elements, they are either: i) preconditioned, ii) multivariate, iii) spatially compounding or iv) temporally compounding (Zscheischler et al., 2020). These events/extremes include the complex spatiotemporal dynamics from the meteorological hazards (Aleksandrova et al., 2024).

The term ‘**Framing**’ in the context of climate attribution refers to which attribution question is being asked (Stott et al., 2016). The attribution question may be very different depending on the definition of the event. Taking a storm that brings extreme rainfall to a region as an example, the event definition could be either the rainfall total seen over the region for any event (the variable of interest for a probabilistic attribution method), or the rainfall total for a storm with the same dynamics as the event (the variable of interest for a storyline attribution method). These are two different ‘Framings’ of the same event, leading to two different attribution studies. Framing the attribution question differently can lead to different answers, even if they are compatible, as shown in Otto et al., (2012) for the 2010 Russian Heatwave.

In attribution a ‘**counterfactual climate**’ is often compared to a ‘factual climate’ (current climate). The term ‘**counterfactual climate**’ or ‘**counterfactuals**’ in the context of attribution refers to a climate where there is minimal or no human influence on the climate (Stott et al., 2016). These can be model simulations where

greenhouse gases and aerosols are kept at pre-industrial levels, with only natural forcings changing over time (Ciavarella et al., 2018). These could also be alternative observations, created using statistical analysis of long-term trends in climate variables such as in Mengel et al., (2021). Or more recently alternative forecasts with the climate signal removed from the initial conditions such as in Leach et al., (2024).

Additionally, the current climate is often compared to a **'future climate'**, which could cover any range of warming scenarios in the future. In some cases, the literature may refer to the 'future climate' as a counterfactual climate. However, for clarity, in this report, a 'counterfactual climate' refers only to a climate where there is minimal or no human influence on the climate.

1.2 Structure of this report

In section 2, we provide an overview of common methodologies used in climate attribution, covering a range of approaches. We then examine their individual suitability for compound attribution, providing a critical review of each method. In the final part of this section, we provide a potential framework for choosing the most suitable attribution method for examination of a specific compound event. Section 3 provides a list of climate and observation datasets that could be applied to the methods in section 2 for compound attribution. Section 4 describes weather pattern data available that could be used in combination with those datasets. Finally, in the last section the use case studies are listed with a list of potential attribution methods that could be used for each study.

2. Attribution methods overview

2.1. Framing the attribution

There are a large range of attribution methods that can be applied to a specific event, these methods can ask different questions and hence can provide very different results for the same event (Stott et al., 2016). Otto et al., (2012) shows an example of two different attribution studies on the same event, where different attribution questions were asked, leading to different, albeit compatible results. One study on the 2010 Russian heatwave asked how much more likely it was to get a new temperature record due to climate change, showing a fivefold increase in likelihood (Rahmstorf and Coumou 2011). However, another study asked whether this event was possible in a world without climate change, finding it was possible, and that large scale circulation played a major role (Dole et al., 2011).

We refer to the choice of attribution question as 'Framing'. A storyline method may focus on how climate change influenced the thermodynamic aspect of an event only (hence conditioned on the dynamics of the event), whereas probabilistic methods tend to examine how climate change is influencing both the large-scale dynamics and thermodynamic factors (Shepherd, 2016). Probabilistic (unconditioned) and storyline (highly conditioned) methods are at the extremes of the spectrum of conditionality (Stott et al., 2016) shown in Figure 1, there are a range of methods that can be applied with different levels of conditionality. Therefore, it is important for each case study to be aware of which attribution question the authors want to answer whilst choosing the method and their usefulness to stakeholders. If the stakeholder is interested in the overall risk of flooding, a probabilistic approach may provide more useful information, because it examines a wide range of events that could bring flooding. However, if the stakeholder is interested in the change of risk in impacts for the specific event, the storyline methodology is better suited in most cases, because it more closely examines the nature of the event of interest. The data availability, complexity, and nature of the given event may make specific methods more beneficial compared to others. Ideally, a wide range of methodologies would be used for a specific event, to both assess confidence in the results and develop a wider understanding of the role climate change had in the event, with both approaches providing valuable and complementary information. In

some cases this may not be feasible however, the pros and cons of the storyline and probabilistic approaches are given below.

Figure 1: Diagram showing a range of common attribution methods and their relative conditionality. The length of each box represents the range of conditionality that can be answered using the attribution method.

Probabilistic approaches: Addresses how climate change has influenced the event in question taking both large-scale dynamics and thermodynamic factors into account and hence giving a more complete answer. These approaches are sometimes referred to as likelihood or risk-based approaches. Probabilistic approaches are more useful for stakeholders and policymakers interested in disaster risk reduction (Otto et al., 2016). This has two potential challenges, however. Firstly, to address low signal-to-noise ratios from internal variability and to cover a range of climate conditions and events, large enough ensembles of climate data are required (Jezequel et al., 2018). These would have to be even larger for multivariate events (compound attribution) than univariate events, given multiple extremes are being examined and not just one extreme, especially where the variables examined are not strongly correlated (Bevacqua et al., 2023). Secondly, they require confidence that the circulation changes are being correctly captured by climate models, which are challenging to validate (Trenberth et al., 2015). The results of these approaches are often given in the form of the change in the intensity and/or risk-ratio. The risk-ratio is defined as the probability of an event (at least as extreme) occurring in the current climate, divided by the equivalent probability in a counterfactual climate (Harrington et al., 2018).

Storyline approaches: Addresses how climate change has influenced a specific event rather than a class of events. This approach examines how and to what extent climate change has influenced the thermodynamic and local-dynamical processes involved in the event, with the large-scale synoptics leading to the event remaining fixed. This approach is well suited to events whose extremity is linked to unusual weather patterns or combination of dynamical drivers, where that type of event may not be well represented or represented at all in climate model runs (Leach et al., 2024). This approach may also avoid the issue of noise from natural variability, caused by variation in the large-scale dynamics, leaving it easier to measure the climate change aspect that there is more confidence on (i.e. Thermodynamic aspect) (Shepherd et al., 2016). Furthermore, less data is required for this approach as only factual and counterfactual events similar to the test case are required, which partly addresses the challenge of requiring far greater data samples in compound attribution.

It is important to note that it only partially answers the attribution question, with any influence on changes in large-scale dynamics ignored. However, the results are still likely to be of interest to the general public and policymakers (Leach et al., 2024).

2.2. Attribution Method Examples

Figure 2 shows a wide range of attribution methods with options across the spectrum of conditionality. In the section below we discuss some of these options in more detail, with commentary on how well they are suited to or in some cases can be applied to compound attribution. Studies such as Leach et al., (2024) and Buschow et al., (2024) have shown that the risk ratio of the event changes based on the level of conditionality, with higher risk ratios for approaches with more conditioning. Therefore, we suggest, if practical, considering examining both approaches, which can provide the most robust understanding of both the event and overall risk. It is also important to caveat, that the diagram is an overview, and that there are likely to be alternative attribution methods not included that could be used.

Figure 2: Diagram showing a range of attribution methods for different attribution framings and available datasets.

2.2.1. Probabilistic

Distribution scaling with covariate (WWA method): This method uses several observation datasets and multi-model ensemble transient(continuous) datasets to examine how the probability and intensity of exceeding the variable magnitude associated with the event in question has changed. To do this, it uses a covariate approach which scales the distribution of the variable examined with global mean surface temperature (GMST) (Philip et al., 2020). The variable is normally in the form of annual maxima (such as daily maximum temperature) and there is flexibility in the choice of the corresponding distribution dependent on the variable chosen. All models undergo validation tests and those that fail are not included in the analysis (Philip et al., 2020). The datasets do not require counterfactual runs, only long transient runs. This approach is designed for univariate events and can only be applied to compound events if the multivariate problem is reduced to a univariate problem by producing a compound metric. A good example of this is Barnes et al., 2023 which uses the wildfire index to combine multiple variables into one.

Factual vs Counterfactual observations (ATTRICI): The method uses a factual set of observations, and a counterfactual set of observations based on long-term trends. The counterfactuals are created for climate variables that correlate well to global mean temperature (GMT), with the method using GMT to detrend the factual observations (Mengel et al., 2021). The benefits of the methodology include the preservation of internal variability and extreme events. In addition, the datasets can be easily translated into impacts with no

bias correction required. However, for certain multivariate events, the length of the observations record may be too short in some cases (Bevacqua et al., 2023).

Factual vs Counterfactual using Large Ensembles: This methodology fits distributions to and compares time-slices of factual climate runs (that are assumed stationary) with counterfactual climate runs for the variable(s) of interest to calculate how the frequency and intensity of such extremes have changed due to anthropogenic climate change. The counterfactual time slice can either consist of counterfactual runs over the time of the event or a sufficiently long time slice further back in time, representative of a world with limited influence of anthropogenic climate change. This method is very well suited to compound event attribution as very large datasets can be used in the analysis that cover a range of events and combinations of extremes. Both Bevacqua et al., 2023 and Zscheischler and Lehner, (2022) recommend this methodology using SMILEs (Single Model Initial-condition Large Ensembles) for attribution of compound events, for this reason. They suggest the use of SMILEs for compound attribution instead of multiple models with single-to-few members, to avoid the complexity of model variability in addition to that of natural variability when analyzing the attribution results (Bevacqua et al., 2023). It also allows for more robust model validation of the extremes, due to the larger sample size (Zscheischler and Lehner, 2022).

2.2.2. Semi-conditioned

Factual vs Counterfactual using analogues method: The analogues method extracts events from factual and counterfactual climates in either observations or climate datasets, with the same large-scale dynamics. The levels of conditionality can vary from extracting all blocking events (Buschow et al., 2024) to extracting fewer events with very conditioned atmospheric circulation patterns (Faranda et al., 2021). This method can be useful in understanding how changes within weather patterns are being affected by climate change such as persistence and seasonality, in addition to thermodynamic changes (Faranda et al., 2021). Analogues can be chosen using a range of metrics, including weather pattern data, that is described in detail in section 4. Analogues can be extracted from large ensembles meaning that there are many samples of extreme multivariate events, which is ideal for compound attribution. Using weather patterns as a selection criterion is also useful for modelling impacts in reducing sample size to the relevant events, without basing it on combinations of several variables. On occasions where the event is very extreme and there are not enough similar events in the ensembles, this method may not be appropriate.

Factual vs Counterfactual using atmosphere-only large ensembles: This is very similar to the 'Factual vs Counterfactual using Large Ensembles' from the risk-based methods. However, instead of using long coupled climate model runs, atmosphere-only models conditioned on sea-surface temperatures (SSTs) are used. This has the benefit that atmosphere only model runs are cheaper and quicker to run, and hence even greater ensemble sizes can be produced (Stott et al., 2016), which is ideal for compound event attribution. One option is to carry out an attribution method similar to the risk-based version, using a time slice approach. However, in some cases where the sample size is large enough for the atmosphere-only ensembles, attribution can be carried out for that particular year conditioned on the SSTs (Ciavarella et al., 2018). Model biases in atmosphere only models may be reduced compared to coupled-models due to the prescription of SSTs, however the major drawback being that atmosphere ocean coupling is not represented (Stott et al., 2016). Therefore, this method is less well suited to events relying on the representation of this coupling.

2.2.3. Storylines

Forecast attribution: Forecast attribution uses operational forecasts and perturbed versions of these forecasts with adjusted ocean temperatures and CO₂ levels for a world with both more and less climate change (Leach et

al., 2021). These can be initialized anytime from four months to a few days before the event (Leach et al., 2024), and hence the methodology can apply the conditionality most appropriate to the event in question. For longer lead-up times this can be considered a more probabilistic approach. It is important to note, that an adjustment period is required for the atmosphere in the perturbed forecasts to catch up with the applied perturbations in ocean heat and CO₂ levels, which can take place over a timescale of days (Leach et al., 2024), which may limit the degree of conditionality that the event can be attributed at. The benefits of this method include, less biases compared to climate models, higher spatial-temporal resolution than most CMIP models and will take into account unusual dynamics that may make the event in question rare (Leach et al., 2024). This has the benefit for compound attribution that there should be many extreme events for the analysis, however, there may be smaller overall sample sizes (51 ensemble members max currently covering the specific year), compared to large ensembles such as SMILES or CMIP that could have 50 plus ensembles covering decades. Forecasts not requiring the bias correction that climate models do is also beneficial for the impact modelling side, especially given the difficulty of bias correcting variables with strong dependencies between each other. Counterfactual forecasts must be created for the event and hence may not be immediately available in most cases.

Spectral nudging and similar highly conditioned methods: These methods involve imposing the dynamics of the observed event on factual and counterfactual simulations, allowing an attribution of the thermodynamic aspect of the event. One way of doing this is through spectral nudging; where the large-scale dynamics in the free atmosphere are nudged towards observations, allowing the lower atmosphere to respond to that (van Garderen et al., 2021). The counterfactual simulations have their SSTs adjusted by removing the climatological warming, with their greenhouse gas levels also adjusted and are nudged in the same way as the factual simulations (van Garderen et al., 2021). The method would be most beneficial to events where the large-scale dynamics and how they unfolded played a key role in how extreme the event was and its corresponding impacts. A good example of this is Goulart et al., (2024), which examines the compound impacts of Hurricane Sandy using the spectral nudging method. This method allows for sufficient examples of extremes within both factual and counterfactual simulations to do the attribution. The disadvantage of this and similar methods is that factual and counterfactual simulations must be produced for the event in question and are unlikely to be readily available.

2.3 Choosing attribution methods

The choice of attribution method for a given compound event case study is not trivial in most cases. Figure 3 shows a workflow for choosing the most suitable method for a given compound event, starting with the framing and then choosing the best method available for that framing. The steps are as follows, and we use the 2013-2014 winter storms in the UK as a case study to provide an example of how it could be used. The compound event includes a sequence of storms over a short time-period, resulting in the compound impacts of inland and coastal flooding (McCarthy and Kendon 2015).

Figure 3: Workflow for choosing best suited attribution method for a compound event.

Step 1: Which attribution question do we want to answer?

In the case of the 2013-14 storms in the UK, there were multiple storms, hence we are not looking at one specific event rather a whole season containing a number of events. Therefore, a storyline approach is not well suited to this event, and we would be more interested in calculating the probability of exceeding such an accumulation of rainfall over any winter and examining how that follows through to impacts. Hence, we want to use an approach on the probabilistic side of the spectrum.

Step 2: Which available methods in this category are suitable for compound attribution?

One option available includes factual vs counterfactual for large ensembles using SMILES and/or observations. This is well suited for compound attribution given the large sample size. Trend based approaches using large ensembles, is an alternative method that could work for compound attribution. The other methods on the

probabilistic side of the spectrum include multi-model ensemble scaling with covariate. This approach requires a univariate input, which is less suitable for compound attribution in this case, as we are then unable to examine the compound aspect of flooding (Coastal and Fluvial), even if we can combine the storms into a univariate rainfall total. Given the large natural variability associated with winter rainfall in the UK, a large sample size is required and hence other methodological options that rely on observations predominantly (a much smaller sample size) are not as well suited for compound attribution of this event. Therefore, we determine that the factual vs counterfactual for large ensembles using SMILES and observations methodology is the best method for this case study.

Step 3: Are the datasets required of sufficient quality?

The intention is to use hydrological modelling to simulate stream flows associated with the event, in addition to modelling the coastal flooding. To do this, the input rainfall into the model needs to be of sufficient quality to allow for realistic simulation of flows and flooding. In addition to this a large sample size is required to capture a range of events and address the large natural variability seen in UK winter rainfall. Using SMILES which contain large sample sizes (including at least one at sufficiently high resolution (12km) over the UK (e.g. Leduc et al., 2019)), this is a potential option. Multi-model ensemble data such as HighResMIP may be of suitable quality, given its increased resolution compared to CMIP models. More detailed model validation checks are required to check the sufficient quality of data and its suitability, however.

Step 4: Which option is best for translation to impacts?

We will use hydrological models, that will produce flood maps for the estimation of impacts. The main challenge is likely to be calibrating the river flow model for the input rainfall data. It is potentially much easier to calibrate it for one large ensemble than a multi-model ensemble where there is a lot of variability between models. It is also likely that some bias correction is needed, and it is much easier to bias correct individual ensembles than multi-model ensembles. Therefore, we intend to use the method that uses SMILES rather than a multi-model ensemble such as HighResMIP/CMIP.

3. Datasets for climate attribution studies

There are a number of datasets that can be used for climate attribution, impact attribution and compound hazard modelling. Work Package 1, “D1.1 – Guidelines for compound extremes modelling in current and future climates” provides an inventory of datasets that are most appropriate for compound hazard modelling (Aleksandrova et al., 2024), which is attached in Annex A of this report. Below are some details on additional datasets not included in the inventory that could become available and are appropriate for climate and impact attribution studies.

Event specific datasets: Storyline approaches often use simulations of the specific event in question in the form of both factual and counterfactual simulations. An example of this is forecast attribution, where counterfactual forecasts can be produced for specific events of interest such as in Leach et al., (2024). This data may be publicly available for specific events, already examined in an attribution context. In cases where climate models are unable to capture the type of event of interest, creating counterfactual forecasts for the specific event using high levels of conditioning may be advantageous.

Statistical/ML downscaled datasets: Climate datasets such as CMIP6 are being downscaled to higher spatial resolution such as Gebrechorkos et al., 2023. Both statistical and dynamical downscaling (global-to-local) for

the hazard is also being carried out in WP1 of COMPASS as these downscaling methods may not lead to the same outcomes. Similarly, bias correction is an important step for hazard modelling. WP1 will explore the impacts of different bias correction methods, comparing univariate methods to recent multivariate ones.

4. Weather pattern data

The term “*weather pattern*” can be used to describe a defined circulation type over a region. In the UK, Lamb (1972) described seven basic daily weather types: cyclonic, anticyclonic, northerly, easterly, southerly, westerly and north-westerly. Recently, the Met Office objectively derived a set of 30 weather patterns for the UK and surrounding European area (MO30; Neal et al. 2016), which are predominantly used in operational weather forecasting (e.g. Buizza et al. 2007) but has also been used to address a number of research questions. The large number of patterns (30) also allows them to be grouped flexibly based off of a specific type of event and its associated impacts.

Extreme weather events are often linked to large-scale atmospheric flow or a specific “weather pattern”. The Met Office developed a set of 30 weather patterns representative of circulation over the UK and European domain (Neal et al. 2016) and shown in Figure 4. These weather patterns were applied to ERA5 data to generate daily historical weather pattern classifications from 1950 to 2020 (Neal et al. 2020). As mentioned, these are predominantly used in operational weather forecasting (e.g. Buizza et al. 2007), but there is also a significant amount of research using these weather patterns to assess extreme events such as: the increased likelihood of coastal flooding (Neal et al. 2018), regional extreme precipitation (Richardson et al. 2020), increased volcanic ash risk (Harrison et al. 2022), temperature-related excess mortality (Huang et al. 2020), amongst others. While Hendry et al (2019) have considered the drivers of compound flooding events around the UK coast, we aim here to extend this approach to consider the different typologies of compound events: multivariate, spatial, temporal and preconditioned (Zscheischler et al. 2020).

Weather patterns can also be used to understand variability on climatic time scales. The UK Met Office Global Climate Model, HadGEM3, was combined with the Met Office set of 30 weather patterns for a historical period (1900–2010) and out to the end of the 21st Century (Pope et al. 2021). This work enabled wider research to consider potential future risk from extreme events, including: extension of the UK summer and its impact on autumn precipitation (Cotterill et al. 2022) and comparison of weather pattern changes and future sea level rise on coastal flood risk (Perks et al. 2023). Task T2.1 aims to carry out analysis of the stationarity of weather types, developing understanding of any temporal change in weather type characteristics within the broader context of a changing climate.

Additionally, the approach used to generate the Met Office UK & European weather patterns has been applied to other parts of the world. Neal et al (2019) developed a set of optimal weather pattern definitions over India, to assess variability in precipitation, which was later applied to high-impact weather forecasting in the region (Neal et al. 2022). Ireland et al (2024), produced a set of weather patterns over South Africa to support impact-based forecasting of heatwave events. Steele et al (2023) also used the same weather typing approach but applied it to the sea surface height fields to improve the prediction of Loop Current and Eddy Regimes in the Gulf of Mexico.

Combining analysis of weather types and changes in large-scale drivers is well suited toward developing a conditional approach to the attribution of compound events. The understanding gained will feed into the choice of attribution method, and lead to more robust analyses.

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Figure 4: The Met Office 30 defined weather patterns. Mean sea level pressure (MSLP) anomalies (hPa) plotted as filled contours and MSLP mean values (2 hPa intervals) plotted as black lines. Source: Neal et al (2016)

5. Assessing suitable methodologies for COMPASS Use Cases

This section specifies suitable attribution methods and outputs for each Use Case (UC) defined in Phase I of the project. Each Use Case contains information on the potential; attribution framing, attribution method, metrics/variables, datasets and impact modelling involved.

Table 1: Summary of Use Cases (UC) for Phase I of the COMPASS project. Source: Aleksandrova et al., (2024)

UC no.	Spatiotemporal dynamics considered	Major hazard types	Event name and date	Region
1	Multivariate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coastal flooding (tide, storm surge) - Wind 	Extratropical cyclone - storm Xynthia (2010)	France
2a	Temporally compounding, Multivariate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wind - Pluvial flooding - Coastal flooding (tide, storm surge) 	Winter 2013/2014	United Kingdom
2b	Temporally compounding, Multivariate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Heatwave - Drought - Wildfires 	Summer 2022	United Kingdom
3a	Multivariate, spatially and temporally compounding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coastal flooding (tide, storm surge, waves) - Wind - Pluvial flooding - River flooding 	Tropical cyclone Idai, Kenneth and Freddy	Mozambique
3b	Multivariate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drought - Saltwater intrusion 	2015/2016	Mozambique
4	Temporally compounding and Multivariate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pluvial flooding - River flooding - Coastal flooding (storm surge) 	Tropical cyclone Eta and Iota	Caribbean
5	Temporally compounding and Multivariate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Heatwave - Drought 	No specific event (operational demonstrator)	Poland

UC 1 – Extra-tropical Storm Xynthia

Table 2: Potential attribution methods for Extra-tropical Storm Xynthia in 2010 in France

2010 Xynthia storm	Framing	Method	Metrics	Datasets	Impact Modelling
First Choice Method (windstorm)	Probabilistic	Factual vs counterfactual time slice	Change in long-term extreme value distribution including seasonal changes (tsEVA method, Mentaschi et al. 2016)	ERA5/ERA5-Land	Yes (economic damage and fatalities)
Second Choice Method (windstorm)	Probabilistic	Factual vs counterfactual time slice	ATTRICI method	Downscaled ERA5/ERA5-Land	Yes (economic damage and fatalities)
First Choice Method (flooding)	Probabilistic	Factual vs counterfactual time slice	tsEVA method for storm surge + climate-induced sea level rise	ERA5 + sea level rise datasets	Yes (economic damage, people affected, fatalities)

UC 2a – Winter storms of 2013/14

Table 3: Potential attribution methods for Winter Storm of 2013/14 in the UK

2013-2014 UK Storms	Framing	Method	Metrics	Datasets	Impact Modelling
First Choice Method	Probabilistic	Factual vs counterfactual time slice	Rainfall and Wind (Coast flooding and inland flooding)	SMILEs	Yes (River flow model and coastal model)

UC 2b – Heatwaves and droughts of summer 2022

Table 4: Potential attribution methods for drought-heatwave of 2022 in the UK

2022 UK Drought-Heatwave	Framing	Method	Metrics	Datasets	Impact Modelling
First Choice Method	Probabilistic	Factual vs counterfactual time slice	Nine-month effective rainfall DJFMAMJJA (River flows) and summer temperatures	SMILEs	Yes (Low River flows)
Second Choice Method	Semi-conditioned	Factual vs Counterfactual time slice runs conditioned on SSTs	Nine-month effective rainfall DJFMAMJJA and summer temperatures	HadGEM3-A (2022 years only)	No

UC 3a –Tropical Cyclones Idai, Kenneth and Freddy

Table 5: Potential attribution methods for tropical cyclone Idai, Kenneth and Freddy in Mozambique

TC Idai, Kenneth & Freddy	Framing	Method	Metrics	Datasets	Impact Modelling
First Choice Method	Storylines	Factual vs counterfactual	Rainfall, storm surge and wind (Coastal, pluvial and fluvial flooding)	Reanalysis rainfall, wind and pressure data, adjusted with counterfactual assumptions	Yes (coastal, hydrological, flood inundation and flood damage model)
Second Choice Method	Storylines	Factual vs. counterfactual	Rainfall, storm surge and wind (Coastal, pluvial and fluvial flooding)	Output from a spectrally nudged RCM using factual and counterfactual CMIP forcing	Yes
Third Choice Method	Probabilistic	Covariate scaling WWA-method	Rain and wind	CMIP	No

UC 4 – Tropical cyclones Eta and Iota

Table 6: Potential attribution methods for sequential tropical cyclones Eta and Iota in the Caribbean

Eta and Iota	Framing	Method	Metrics	Datasets	Impact Modelling
First Choice Method	Storylines	Factual vs counterfactual	Rainfall and Wind (Coast flooding and inland flooding)	GloFAS Global Food Monitoring (Sentinel-1), NOAA/UNOSAT Global flood maps (VIIRS), IBTrACS, ERA5 Re-analysis, TC storm surge, rainfall, and sea-level counterfactuals	Yes (coastal, hydrological, flood inundation) Possibly health impact modeling and population displacement

UC 5 – Heatwave and Drought

Table 7: Potential attribution methods for operational demonstrator

Operational demonstrator (Poland)	Framing	Method	Metrics	Datasets	Impact Modelling
<u>First Choice Method (Heatwave and Drought)</u>	<u>Probabilistic</u>	<u>Factual vs counterfactual time slice</u>	<u>ATTRICI method</u>	<u>ERA5/ERA5-Land</u>	<u>Yes (crop yield losses and fatalities)</u>

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Annex A: Inventory of Observations and Climate Datasets from D1.1

This annex contains section 3.1 from the Deliverable D1.1 ‘Guidelines for compound extremes modelling in current and future climates’ Aleksandrova et al., (2024). The section contains an inventory of observational, forecast and climate model datasets, that could be used for attribution studies.

3.1 Climate dataset categories for attribution studies

When selecting relevant climate datasets for compound hazard modelling, it is useful to consider the type of desired attribution method and thus requirements for the datasets to construct both the factual, the observed event that serves as a baseline for the analysis, and the counterfactuals, a series of alternative realizations of the observed event, e.g., in a world without climate change (Stott et al., 2016) . Hazard modelling for the factual and counterfactual events can stem from the following three broad categories of climate datasets:

Observation-based datasets from gauges and stations or reanalysis datasets. Reanalysis climate data is combined with observations and gap-filled by combining them with historical data from short-range weather forecast models to provide a gridded dataset. In climate science, these datasets are the closest to the “ground truth” for a global scale analysis. Counterfactuals can be generated by removing temporal trend, or after regressing out the change based on another covariate, for e.g. global mean temperature. The temporal coverage of the data should be long enough to include records with low human influence. Usually a counterfactual period of 30 years, usually 1950 – 1979, to account for natural variability is used to represent observational-based counterfactuals without climate change (Faranda et al., 2022) .

Climate model-based datasets from fully coupled climate models to only sea surface temperature-forced model. Climate models can be global or region specific but cover larger timescales than reanalysis datasets from preindustrial times to future projections (generally ~1850-2100). Two ways to generate robust counterfactuals are using a large ensemble of simulations with multiple climate models (at least > 6 models; Hermans et al. (2024)) or using a Single Model Initial-condition Large Ensemble (SMILE; Bevacqua et al. (2023)) consisting of multiple simulations with the same climate model but with different initial states, or both.

Forecast-based datasets from numerical weather prediction (NWP) models, or forecast models. They process current weather to predict future weather at in the short future (upcoming hours to days). These estimates are updated, usually every 6 to 12 hours, and often do not need bias correction unlike climate model based datasets. The main advantage of a NWP model over a climate model is that, they can capture both the important physical processes and their external influence that lead to the event. This is of course provided that the model itself is reliable for the extreme considered. Counterfactuals can then be created by perturbing the initial and boundary conditions of the model. Additionally, ensemble boosting methods can be used to explore plausible alternative realisations of events, potentially with higher intensity (Gessner et al., 2023) . Forecast data have shorter timescales but are known to resolve extreme events well due to their high spatial and short-term temporal resolution while account well for natural variability.

This section provides an overview of the most commonly used large scale gridded climate datasets, distinguishing between reanalysis data (3.1.1), modelled climate data (3.1.2) and forecast climate data (3.1.3). Depending on the type of hazard modelling and attribution method, datasets can be selected based on spatial and temporal coverage and resolution and covered climate variables. We do not provide an exhaustive list of climate datasets but rather highlight the most important categories and large-scale datasets commonly used in compound event modelling.

3.1.1. Reanalysis climate data

Multiple institutions and organization have developed gridded reanalysis datasets where they combine observations with modelled data to obtain a consistent product, which can be global or region specific. The

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most commonly used reanalysis dataset is ERA5(-Land) developed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF).

Table 31: Global or continental gridded reanalysis climate data sources commonly used for hazard modelling

Dataset	Details
Global	
ERA5	The ECMWF Reanalysis v5 (ERA5) datasets is the state-of-the-art gridded atmospheric reanalysis, which is complete and consistent across the globe and covers most atmospheric, ocean-wave and land-surface variables. Spatial resolution: 0.25° (and 0.5° for ocean-waves), vertical resolution of 137 levels Temporal coverage: 1940 – present, hourly (updated daily)
ERA5-Land	The ECMWF Reanalysis v5 - Land (ERA5-Land) is a gridded reanalysis dataset, covering hydrological and biospheric land variables. Spatial resolution: 0.1°, vertical coverage from 2 m above the surface level, to a soil depth of 289 cm divided in 4 levels Temporal coverage: 1950 – present, hourly (updated monthly with a delay of about three months).
FNL	The NCEP FNL (Final) Operational Global Analysis data is a gridded reanalysis dataset based on the GFS forecast data, combined with other observational data sources using NSF NCAR's Global Data Assimilation System (GDAS), covering several atmospheric, oceanic, and land-surface variables. Spatial resolution: 1°, vertical resolution of 26 layers Temporal coverage: 1999 – present, 6-hourly
NCEP-NCAR	The National Centers for Environmental Prediction and the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCEP-NCAR) Reanalysis-1 is a gridded reanalysis dataset, covering a wide range of atmospheric variables. Spatial resolution: 2.5°, vertical resolution of 17 levels Temporal coverage: 1948 – present, 6-hourly
MERRA-2	The Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications, Version 2 (MERRA-2) is a reanalysis dataset developed by NASA, covering atmospheric, oceanic and land surface variables. Spatial resolution: 0.5° x 0.625°, vertical resolution of 72 levels Temporal resolution: 1980 – present, hourly
JRA-55	The Japanese 55-year Reanalysis (JRA-55) is a gridded reanalysis dataset, covering atmospheric and land surface variables. Spatial resolution: 1.25°, vertical resolution of 60 levels Temporal resolution: 1958 – 2024, 3- to 6-hourly
20CRv3	The NOAA/CIRES/DOE 20th Century Reanalysis version 3 (20CRv3) is a gridded reanalysis dataset covering mainly atmospheric variables. Spatial resolution: 1°, vertical resolution of 28 levels Temporal resolution: 1836 – 2015, 3-hourly
CFSR	The Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR) from National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) is a reanalysis product of a coupled atmosphere-ocean-land surface-sea ice of a forecasting system, covering atmospheric and ocean variables. Spatial resolution: 0.25° to 0.5°, vertical resolution of 40 to 64 levels Temporal resolution: 1979 – 2010, 6-hourly
Region specific	
UERRA	The Uncertainties in Ensembles of Regional ReAnalysis (UERRA) dataset covering Europe combining analysis from the EURRA-HARMONIE and MESCAN-SURFEX systems, and covering surface and near-surface essential climate variables. Spatial resolution: 5.5 – 11.1 km, single vertical level Temporal resolution: 1961 – 2019, 6-hourly
CERRA	The Copernicus European Regional ReAnalysis (CERRA) dataset aims to produce and deliver a regional reanalysis (RRA) for Europe forced with ERA5, adding in-situ observations and satellite information, and covers surface and near-surface essential climate variables. There is also a specific CERRA-Land dataset including high density surface observations. Another complementary dataset covering the uncertainty of all

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	<p>output parameters is from an Ensemble of Data Assimilation is CERRA-EDA.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 5.5 – 11.1 km, single vertical level Temporal resolution: 1984 – 2021, 3- to 6-hourly (new data added by the end of 2024)</p>
CHIRPS	<p>The Climate Hazards Group InfraRed Precipitation with Station data (CHIRPS) is a 35+ year quasi-global gridded rainfall data set, covering 50°S-50°N (and all longitudes). The dataset is based on rain gauge data and satellite observations.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 0.05°, single vertical level Temporal resolution: 1981 – present, daily</p>
JCR MARS	<p>The JRC MARS Meteorological Database is a dataset covering Europe and based on observations from weather stations and developed for agricultural studies, covering atmospheric and vegetation related (e.g., potential evaporation from crop canopy) variables.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 25 km Temporal resolution: 1979 – 2023, daily</p>

3.1.2. Modelled climate data

Modelled climate data is used here as a broad term for continuous long-term simulated climate data for multiple decades to centuries. There are many climate models available, simulating multiple scenarios with different initial conditions, leading to a lot of different datasets. The Climate Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) is the state-of-the-art model intercomparison and is currently in its seventh cycle. Here, some of the most known global and regional climate model datasets are presented but does not include a complete overview.

Table 32: Global or continental gridded climate data sources commonly used for hazard modelling

Dataset	Details
Modelled climate data	
CMIP5 , CMIP6 and CMIP7	<p>The Climate Model Intercomparison version 5 (CMIP5) and version 6 (CMIP6) are state-of-the-art multimodel ensembles (version 7 (CMIP7) is currently being developed) providing projections of historical periods and future climate change under different scenarios of greenhouse gas emissions, covering atmospheric, oceanic and land surface variables.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: from 0.125° to 5°, single pressure levels (1 - 1000 hPa) Temporal resolution: 1850 – 2100 (CMIP6), 1850 – 2300 (CMIP5, daily)</p>
SMILEs	<p>A single model initial-condition large ensemble (SMILE) are datasets of a single global or regional climate model (GCM/RCM) run with a range of initial conditions to capture the natural variability of a system separate from external forcings. These runs are also included in CMIP. These ensembles enable a more accurate estimation of the probability distribution, including extreme values.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: from 0.7° to 2.8° Temporal resolution: 1850 – 2100 (varies per SMILE)</p>
CORDEX	<p>The Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) dataset provides high-resolution regional climate simulation for 14 regions across the globe, covering atmospheric, oceanic and land surface variables, depending on the domain. The highest resolution data is available for the Europe domain.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 0.44° up to 0.11° Temporal resolution: 1950 to 2100, 3-hourly to daily</p>
ISIMIP	<p>The Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP) are bias-adjusted climate datasets, and is based on CMIP data. ISIMIP also provides socioeconomic data, static geographic data and detrended, counterfactual climate datasets.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 0.5° Temporal resolution: varies per dataset</p>
PRIMAVERA	<p>The Process-based climate simulation: Advances in high-resolution modeling and European climate risk assessments high-resolution climate datasets consists of data from both atmosphere-only and coupled climate runs, covering atmospheric and oceanic variables. The models are also integrated in CMIP6.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 25 km Temporal resolution: 1950 to 2050, extended to 2100 in the future</p>

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ATTRICI	<p>The ATTRIButing Climate Impacts (ATTRICI) is a counterfactual climate dataset for impact attribution and used in ISIMIP, covering atmospheric and land-surface variables.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 0.5° Temporal resolution: 1901 - 2019, daily</p>
HighResMIP	<p>The High Resolution Model Intercomparison Project (HighResMIP) is a SST-forced model ensemble, covering atmospheric, oceanic and land-surface variables. The model ensemble is also incorporated in CMIP6</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 25-50 km Temporal resolution: 1950 - 2050</p>
DestinE	<p>The Destination Earth initiative (DestinE) so far has developed two global datasets from Earth Digital Twins, spanning both historic and future times. The datasets are Digital Twins for Climate Change Adaptation and for forecast for Weather-induced and Geophysical Extremes, covering atmospheric, oceanic and land-surface variables.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 500 m to 50 km, multiple vertical levels Temporal resolution: 1990 – 2040, 5 min to daily</p>
Region specific	
H2020 EUCP	<p>The Horizon2020 European Climate Prediction System (H2020 EUCP) project has developed a high resolution European dataset resulting from Convection Permitting Model (CPM) simulations, covering temperature and precipitation anomalies. The data is separated into multiple domains within Europe.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 2.2 – 3 km Temporal resolution: 1995 – 2060</p>
UKCP	<p>The UK Climate Projections (UKCP) data is a United Kingdom (UK) high resolution dataset, although also having data for the whole globe on a lower resolution, covering atmospheric and some hydrological variables.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 2.2 km (local), 12 km (regional) and 60 km (global) Temporal resolution: 1900 – 2100, hourly to daily</p>
CP4A- Present/ Future	<p>The Convection-Permitting Climate for Africa (CP4A) datasets (Present and Future) are based on high resolution convection permitting climate simulations is, covering atmospheric variables.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 4.5 km Temporal resolution: 1997-2007 (<i>Present</i> dataset), 2095-2105 (<i>Future</i> dataset)</p>

3.1.3. Forecast data

Forecast data takes place on weather timescales and is developed in an iterative manner using model ensembles. When future climate data extends weather time scales, it is referred to as climate projections which can span multiple decades. Usually, historical forecast data is reused for reanalysis datasets. Generally, forecast data closer to present time are more accurate than further in the future, which is also related to higher temporal resolutions in the near- compared to the far-future.

Table 33: Global or continental gridded forecast data sources commonly used for hazard modelling

Forecast data	
GFS	<p>The NCEP GFS 0.25 Degree Global Forecast Grids Historical Archive is, as the name suggests, a gridded global forecast dataset covering several atmospheric, oceanic, and land-surface variables.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 13km to 0.25°, 26 vertical layers Temporal resolution: 15/01/2015 to present+16 days, 3- to 12-hourly (updated daily)</p>
IFS	<p>A subset of the Integrated Forecast System (IFS) global data by ECMWF is publicly available 1 hour after real-time dissemination and consists of multiple datasets with different resolutions, covering atmospheric, oceanic and land-surface variables. The IFS data is used for the ERA5 reanalysis dataset. Recently, also datasets from Artificial Intelligence Forecasting System (AIFS) are made available.</p> <p>Spatial resolution: 0.25°, 13 vertical layers Temporal resolution: present+10 days, 3- to 6-hourly</p>
TIGGE	<p>The THORPEX Interactive Grand Global Ensemble (TIGGE) is an ensemble forecast dataset from ECMWF, specifically covering (extra-/sub-)tropical cyclone tracks. 6-hourly from 2006 to present, providing up to 32-day forecasts.</p>

Deliverable 2.1 - Report on dataset on best-available methods and climate datasets (for climate attribution)

	Spatial resolution: 0.5° to 1.5° Temporal resolution: 2006 - present+32 days, 6-hourly
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